

title	author	journal/conference	year	doi	status
A taxonomy for mining and classifying privacy requirements in issue reports	Pattaraporn Sangaroonsip and Hsa Khanh Dam and Morakot Chotkietkul and Chaiyong Raghithwetsagul and Aditya Ghose	Information and Software Technology	2023	10.1016/j.infsof.2023.107162	ACCEPTED
The CCPA and the GDPR Are Not the Same: Why You Should Understand Both	W. Gregory Voss	CPI Annuity Chronicle	2021		ACCEPTED
Comparing Data Protection Regulation Models of the EU and the US: Which One is More Preferred by the Society?	Raminta Matulytė		2022		ACCEPTED
Análise Comparada entre Regulamentações de Dados Pessoais no Brasil e na União Europeia (LGPD E GDPR) e seus Respectivos Instrumentos de Enforcement	Laila Neves Lorenzon		2021		ACCEPTED
GDPR e LGPD: estudo comparativo	Rebeca de Aguiar Pereira Neves		2021		ACCEPTED
Understanding Philippine National Agency's Commitment on Data Privacy Act of 2012: A Case Study Perspective	Pitogo, Vicente A. and Ching, Michelle Renee D.	ICEEE '18: Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on E-commerce, E-Business and E-Government	2018	10.1145/3237481.3237488	ACCEPTED
Privacy Legislation as Business Risks: How GDPR and CCPA are Represented in Technology Companies' Investment Risk Disclosures	Wong, Richmond Y. and Chong, Andrew and Aspegren, R. Cooper	Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction	2023	10.1145/35279515	ACCEPTED
Understanding Ethics, Privacy, and Regulations in Smart Video Surveillance for Public Safety	Babak Rahimi Arbabli and Amin Danesh Pasho and Ghazal Almazhezi Noghre and Christopher Neff and Amin Ravindran and Hamed Tahabi	Computing Research Repository	2022	10.48550/arXiv.2212.12936	ACCEPTED
Agile Teams' Perception in Privacy Requirements Elicitation: GDPR's compliance in Brazil	Edna Dias Canedo, Angelica Toffano Seidel Calazans, Anderson Jefferson Cerqueira, Pedro Henrique Ribeiro, Eloisa Toffano Seidel Masson Costa	Requirements Engineering	2021	10.1109/RE.2021.00013	ACCEPTED
Guidelines adopted by agile teams in privacy requirements elicitation after the Brazilian general data protection law (LGPD) implementation	Edna Dias Canedo, Angelica Toffano Seidel Calazans, Ian Nery Bandeira, Pedro Henrique Teixeira Costa, Eloisa Toffano Seidel Masson	Requirements Engineering	2022	10.1007/978-0-02-03591-7	ACCEPTED
A systematic study on the impact of GDPR compliance on Organizations	Pedro Machado, Jessyka Vilela, Mariana Peixoto, Carla Silva	SSSI '23: Proceedings of the XIX Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems	2023	10.1145/3592813.3592935	ACCEPTED
The GDPR Compliance and Access Control Systems: Challenges and Research Opportunities	Said Daoudagh, Edna Marchetti	ICISSP: Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy	2022	10.62200/10912030003120	ACCEPTED
Are We There Yet?: Understanding the Challenges Faced in Complying with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Sean Sirur, Jason R. C. Nurse, Helena Webb	Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Multimedia Privacy and Security	2018	10.1145/3287357.3287368	ACCEPTED
The Proposed American Data Privacy and Protection Act in Comparison with GDPR	Julia Kaufmann, Felix Hilgert, Runa Wehthalt	Computer Law Review International	2022	10.9785/4-2022.230505	ACCEPTED
A comparative analysis of personal data protection regulations between the EU and China	Weber, P.A., Zhang, N. and Wu, H.	Electronic Commerce Research	2020	10.1007/s10660-020-09422-3	ACCEPTED
"The Grace Period Has Ended": An Approach to Operationalize GDPR Requirements	Vanessa Ayala-Rivera; Lillana Pasquale	IEEE 26th International Requirements Engineering Conference	2018	10.1109/RE.2018.00023	ACCEPTED
Privacy Laws and Privacy by Design Schemes for the Internet of Things: A Developer's Perspective	Aljaisy, Atheer and Barati, Masoud and Rana, Omer and Perera, Charith	ACM Computing Surveys	2021	10.1145/3450965	ACCEPTED
The Changing Wind of Data Privacy Law: A Comparative Study of the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation and the 2018 California Consumer Privacy Act	Grace Park		2019		ACCEPTED
Why you should care about GDPR in IoT Enterprises & Solutions	Filipe Pires, Osvaldo R. Pacheco, Ricardo T. Martins	18th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies	2019	10.23919/CISIT52073.2021.9476614	ACCEPTED
It's all fun and games, and some legalese: data protection implications for increasing cyber risks of employees through games	Danaja Fabric Povse	CECCO 2018: Proceedings of the Central European Cybersecurity Conference	2018	10.1145/3277570.3277580	ACCEPTED
Towards privacy compliance: A design science study in a small organization	Ze Shi Li, Colin Werner, Neil Ernst, Daniela Damian	Information and Software Technology	2022	10.1016/j.infsof.2022.106868	ACCEPTED
The ethics of facial recognition technologies, surveillance, and accountability in an age of artificial intelligence: a comparative analysis of US, EU, and UK regulatory frameworks	Denise Almeida, Elizabeth Lomas; Konstantin Shmarko	AI Ethics	2022	10.1007/978-0-021-00077-w	ACCEPTED
Using MCDA for selecting criteria of LGPD compliant personal data protection	Renato Caravita Ribeiro, Edna Dias Canedo	dg o 20: The 21st Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research	2020	10.1145/3389656.3389652	ACCEPTED
I'm all ears! Listening to software developers on putting GDPR principles into software development practice	Abdurrahman Alhazmi, Naini Asanka Gamagedara Arachchilage	Personal and Ubiquitous Computing	2021	10.1007/978-0-271-01544-1	ACCEPTED
A comparative analysis between General Data Protection Regulations and California Consumer Privacy Act	Syed Khurum Hussain Nayvi, Komal Bhatol	Journal of Computer Science, Information Technology and Telecommunication Engineering	2023	10.30996/josthe.441.13330	ACCEPTED
We Are Not There Yet: The Implications of Insufficient Knowledge Management for Organizational Compliance	Thomas Sierhan von Danner, Konrad Köling, Reuben Birms; Max Van Kleek, Nigel Shadbolt	Computing Research Repository	2023	10.48550/arXiv.2305.04061	ACCEPTED
A survey on solutions to support developers in privacy-preserving IoT development	Patrick Köhrtreiber, Viktorija Pak, Delphine Reinhardt	Pervasive and Mobile Computing	2022	10.1016/j.pamc.2022.101656	ACCEPTED
Perceptions of ICT Practitioners Regarding Software Privacy	Edna Dias Canedo, Angelica Toffano Seidel Calazans, Eloisa Toffano Seidel Masson; Pedro Henrique; Fernanda Lima	Entropy (Basel)	2020	10.3390/entropy200429	ACCEPTED
GDPR Compliance in the Context of Continuous Integration	Ze Shi Li, Colin Werner, Neil Ernst e Daniela Damian	IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering	2020	10.48550/arXiv.2002.06830	ACCEPTED
Information security frameworks for assessing GDPR compliance in banking industry	Jobe Serrado, Ruben Filipe Perera, Miguel Mira da Silva, Itaias Scalabrin Bianchi	Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance	2020	10.1108/DPRG-02-2020-0019	ACCEPTED
Toward Data Protection by Design: Assessing the Current State of GDPR Disclosure in Web Applications	Abdel-Jawad Abernani, Seppe vanden Broecke, Geert Poels	IEEE 31st International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops	2023	10.1109/REIW57809-2023.00044	ACCEPTED
Challenges Regarding the Compliance with the General Data Protection Law by Brazilian Organizations: A Survey	Canedo, Edna Dias; Ribeiro, Vanessa Coelho; Alarido, Ana Paula de Aguiar; Chaves, Lucas Alexandre Carvalho; Reed, Johann Nicholas; Mendonça, Fabio Lúcio Lopes; de Sousa Jr, Rafael	Computational Science and Its Applications	2021	10.1007/978-3-030-86973_0_31	ACCEPTED
The benefits and challenges of general data protection regulation for the information technology sector	Nazar Portskiy, Flavio Oliveira and Fernando Almeida	Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance	2019	10.1108/DPRG-05-2019-0039	ACCEPTED
A Framework for GDPR Compliance for Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises	Martin Brodin	European Journal for Security Research	2019	10.1007/941125-019-00042-z	ACCEPTED
Making Sense of the General Data Protection Regulation - Four Categories of Personal Data Access Challenges	Cassandra Grundstrom, Karin Vährynen, Netta Iivari, Minna Isomursu	Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences	2019	10.24251/HICSS.2019.605	ACCEPTED
Diagnostic of Data Processing by Brazilian Organizations - A Low Compliance Issue	Salmara Ellen Renner Ferito, Artur Poligara Carvalho, Edna Dias Canedo, Alana Paula Barbosa Mota, Pedro Henrique Teixeira Costa, Anderson Jefferson Cerqueira	Information	2021	10.3390/info12040168	ACCEPTED
"Those things are written by lawyers, and programmers are reading that": Mapping the Communication Gap Between Software Developers and Privacy Experts	Stefan Albert Horstmann, Samuel Domke, Marco Guffesoch, Minky Tran, Yasemin Acar, Veelasha Moonsamy, Alena Naakshina	Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies	2024	10.56553/popets.2024.0010	ACCEPTED
On Understanding How Developers Perceive and Interpret Privacy Requirements Research Preview	Mariana Maia Peixoto, Dayse Ferreira, Mateus Cavalcanti, Carla Silva, Jessyka Vilela, Jobo Araújo, Tony Gorschek	Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality - 26th International Working Conference	2020	10.1007/978-3-030-44429-7_8	ACCEPTED
Privacy Champions in Software Teams: Understanding Their Motivations, Strategies, and Challenges	Mohammad Tahaei, Alisa Frik, Kami Vaniea	CHI '21: Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2021	10.1145/3411764.3445768	ACCEPTED
GDPR Compliance in SMEs: There is much to be done	Maria da Conceição Freitas, Miguel Mira da Silva	Journal of Information Systems Engineering & Management	2018	10.202897/jsem941	ACCEPTED
Ensuring Privacy in the Application of the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD)	Evandro Thalles Vale de Castro, Geovana R. S. Silva, Edna Dias Canedo	SAC '22: The 37th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing	2022	10.1145/3477314.3507023	ACCEPTED
IoT Security and Privacy Challenges from the Developer Perspective	Yaqin Shaheen, Miguel J. Homos; Carlos Rodriguez-Dominguez	14th International Symposium on Ambient Intelligence	2023	10.1007/978-3-031-43461-7_2	ACCEPTED
Privacy Compliance in Software Development: A Guide to Implementing the LGPD Principles	Lucas Dalle Rocha; Geovana Ramos Sousa Silva; Edna Dias Canedo	SAC '23: Proceedings of the 38th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing	2023	10.9753/hic_entelmed.2023.229024	ACCEPTED
Data Protection Officers' Perspectives on Privacy Challenges in Digital Ecosystems	Stephan Wiefeling, Jan Tolstorf, and Luigi Lo Iacono	ESORICS 2022 International Workshops	2022	10.1007/978-3-031-26460-4_13	ACCEPTED
"It may be a pain in the backside but...": Insights into the resilience of business after GDPR	Gerard Buckley, Tristan Caultfield, Ingolfo Becker	NSPW '22: Proceedings of the 2022 New Security Paradigms Workshop	2022	10.1145/3584313.3584320	ACCEPTED
The Critical Success Factors of GDPR Implementation: A Systematic Literature Review	Gonçalo Almeida Teixeira, Miguel Mira da Silva, Ruben Pereira	Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance	2019	10.1108/DPRG-01-2019-0007	ACCEPTED
A review of information privacy laws and standards for secure digital ecosystems	Memoona J. Anwar, Asif Q. Gill, Ghassan Beydoun	Australasian Conference on Information Systems	2018	10.5130/aicis2018.0a	ACCEPTED
The General Data Protection Regulation in Financial Services Industries: How Do Companies Approach the Implementation of the GDPR and What Can We Learn From Their Approaches?	Manuel Holler, Benjamin van Giffen, Seth Benzelt, Matthias Ehrat	82nd Annual Business Researchers Conference	2020		ACCEPTED
A Narrative Review of Factors Affecting the Implementation of Privacy and Security Practices in Software Development	Laysan Nurgaliev; Alisa Frik; Gavin Doherty.	ACM Computing Surveys	2023	10.1145/3589951	ACCEPTED
Developers Say the Darndest Things: Privacy Compliance Processes Followed by Developers of Child-Directed Apps	Noura Alomar, Serge Egelman	Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies	2022	10.2478/popets.2022-0108	ACCEPTED
A Review of GDPR Impacts on Information Security	Hivonen, Paulina	Proceedings of the 26th Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems	2022		ACCEPTED
Navigating the Data Avalanche: Towards Supporting Developers in Developing Privacy-Friendly Children's Apps	Anrushi Ekambaramathan, Jun Zhao, George Chalchoub	Proc. ACM Interact. Mob. Wearable Ubiquitous Technol.	2023	10.1145/3596267	ACCEPTED
"Money makes the world go around": Identifying Barriers to Better Privacy in Children's Apps From Developers' Perspectives	Anrushi Ekambaramathan, Jun Zhao, Max Van Kleek	Proceedings of the 2021 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems	2021	10.1145/3411764.3445599	ACCEPTED